

Study of Universal Screening for Gestational Diabetes Mellitus by Single Step Procedure

Sushma R Shah¹, Aayushi A Suthar², Jayshri R Patel³, Harsh A Suthar⁴, Akash J Patel⁵

¹Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Smt. N.H.L. Municipal Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Smt. N.H.L. Municipal Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

³Assistant Professor, Department of Anesthesia, Ananya College of Medicine and Research, Kalol, Gujarat

⁴Intern, Smt. N.H.L. Municipal Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Smt. N.H.L. Municipal Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Sushma R Shah

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Abstract:

Introduction: Gestational diabetes mellitus is defined as “Carbohydrate intolerance of variable severity with the onset and first recognition during the present pregnancy”.

Aims and Objectives: This prospective study conducted over 1 year aimed to investigate the incidence of glucose intolerance in pregnancy by universal screening by DIPSI criteria as a single step procedure with 75 grams oral glucose and its maternal and perinatal outcomes. The study included antenatal patients between gestational age of 14 and 38 weeks irrespective of parity, excluding known case of diabetes, twins, intrauterine fetal demise at initial visit and gestational age less than 14 weeks and more than 38 weeks.

Results: The incidence of GDM was more with advanced maternal age, obesity and family history of diabetes mellitus. The patients who tested positive by single step screening method were advised MNT and only few patients diagnosed GDM required Insulin as their line of management. The prevalence of polyhydramnios and hypertensive diseases was more in glucose intolerant patients compared to normal patients. Also, the study highlights the increased risk of preterm birth and increase in the birth weight of the babies.

Conclusion: Glucose challenge test by DIPSI criteria is highly sensitive in ruling out GDM cases. Hence the universal screening by single step procedure is convenient, economical and suitable without sacrificing the sensitivity expected for the ideal screening test. In this study the glucose intolerant patients were closely monitored and Medical Nutritional Therapy (MNT) was advised in all which helped to reduce the adverse obstetric and perinatal outcome.

Keywords: Gestational Diabetes Mellitus, Diabetes Mellitus, Screening.

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Introduction

Pregnancy is considered to be a diabetogenic state characterized by exaggerated rate and amount of insulin release, associated with decreased sensitivity to insulin at cellular levels. American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists (ACOG) have emphasized on selective screening. [1] Compared with selective screening, universal screening for GDM detects more cases and improves maternal and offspring prognosis. [2]

As per Ministry of health and family welfare, India, 2018, one of the most populous country globally, rates of GDM are estimated to be 10-14.3% which is much higher than the west. [3] Also there is a risk of cardiovascular complications associated

with dyslipidemia, hypertension and abdominal obesity.

Recurrence of GDM is also documented in subsequent pregnancy. Moreover, the presence of a hyperglycaemic intrauterine environment due to GDM is associated with the development of type 2 diabetes in the offspring. [4]. This is important because of the rising prevalence of type 2 diabetes at younger ages. Early diagnosis and intervention can reduce the adverse perinatal outcomes. [4,5,6] DIPSI (Diabetes in Pregnancy Study Group India) adopted the nonfasting OGTT as a single-step screening and diagnostic test for GDM in India.

Materials and Methods

This is a prospective study of 200 antenatal patients which were randomly selected from OPD at our institute from September 2022 to September 2023. This study was conducted to screen the patients for gestational diabetes mellitus by single step procedure.

Inclusion Criteria: All pregnant patients between gestational age of 14-38 weeks irrespective of age and parity.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Known case of diabetes mellitus.
2. Intrauterine fetal demise at initial visit.
3. Multifetal gestation.

200 patients were randomly selected in gestational age of 14-38 weeks by inclusion and exclusion criteria.

A detailed history was taken regarding family history, past history and regarding current pregnancy. Selected patients were taken and 75 grams of oral glucose in 300 ml water was given irrespective of their fasting status; and 2 hours later blood sugar was taken.

Criteria for diagnosing GDM by WHO criteria of 2 hours blood sugar level of 140 mg % and above is to be diagnosed as GDM. Patients diagnosed as GDM were closely monitored with frequent antenatal checkup. In this study patients with HbA1C >6.5% were considered positive and HbA1C <6.5% were considered negative. Hence to understand the course of pregnancy complications and outcome in patients who tested positive with DIPSI criteria but negative with HbA1C were closely monitored.

Results

Table 1: Age of the Patients and Its Relation with Glucose Intolerance

Age in years	DIPSI+ve HbA1C+ve N=12 (% of n)	DIPSI+ve HbA1C-ve N=16 (% of n)	DIPSI-ve HbA1C-ve N=172 (% of n)
<=20	00	01(6.25%)	05(2.90%)
21-25	01(8.33%)	10(62.5%)	75(43.60%)
26-30	02(16.67%)	05(31.25%)	71(41.28%)
31-35	04(33.33%)	00	12(6.98%)
36-40	04(33.33%)	00	09(5.24%)
>40	01(8.33%)	00	00
Total	12(100%)	16(100%)	172(100%)

In the age group of 31-40 years, 67% of the patients were GDM. In DIPSI negative cases 90% of the cases were in the age group of 21-30 years. Hence as the age advances the possibility of glucose intolerance increases.

Table 2: Body Mass Index of the Patients and Its Relation with Glucose Intolerance

BMI	DIPSI+ve HbA1C+ve N=12 (% of n)	DIPSI+ve HbA1C-ve N=16 (% of n)	DIPSI-ve HbA1C-ve N=172 (% of n)
<18.5	00	00	05(2.90%)
18.5-24.9	06(50%)	03(18.75%)	49(28.48%)
25-29.9	04(33.33%)	11(68.75%)	89(51.75%)
>30	02(16.66%)	02(12.5%)	29(16.87%)
Total	12(100%)	16(100%)	172(100%)

In this study 80% DIPSI negative cases had BMI <30. In patients with BMI>25 there is higher occurrence of glucose intolerance.

Table 3: Maternal Complications and Its Relation with Glucose Intolerance

Maternal complications	DIPSI+ve HbA1C+ve N=12 (% of n)	DIPSI+ve HbA1C-ve N=16 (% of n)	DIPSI-ve HbA1C-ve N=172 (% of n)
Polyhydramnios	03(25%)	01(6.25%)	05(2.90%)
Hypertensive disease	06(50%)	02(12.5%)	12(6.98%)
Thyroid disease	03(25%)	00	27(15.69%)
Eclampsia	00	00	00
Asthma	00	00	01(0.59%)
None	00	13(81.25%)	127(73.84%)
Total	12(100%)	16(100%)	172(100%)

In this study, 73% of the patients who were DIPSI negative had no complications. In the patients who were DIPSI positive but HbA1c negative, 81% patients had no complications as compared to HbA1c positive in

which some complications were higher amongst which hypertensive disease (50%) 8 folds increase in risk and polyhydramnios(25%).

Table 5: Neonatal Complication and Its Relation with Glucose Intolerance

Neonatal complication	DIPSI+ve HbA1C+ve N=12 (% of n)	DIPSI+ve HbA1C-ve N=16 (% of n)	DIPSI-ve HbA1C-ve N=172 (% of n)
Macrosomia	00	00	00
IUGR	00	01(6.25%)	07(4.08%)
Congenital anomalies	02(16.67%)	00	00
Hypoglycemia	00	00	00
Sudden foetal demise	00	00	01(0.58%)
RDS	00	02(12.5%)	03(1.74%)
Shoulder dystocia	00	00	00
None	10(83.33%)	13(81.25%)	161(93.60%)
Total	12(100%)	16(100%)	172(100%)

In our study, there is higher risk of congenital anomalies with established GDM and we did not find any cases of congenital anomaly in DIPSI positive and HbA1c negative patients. The larger study is necessary to establish this correlation.

Table 6: Birth Weight and Its Relation with Glucose Intolerance

Birth weight in kg	DIPSI+ve HbA1C+ve N=12 (% of n)	DIPSI+ve HbA1C-ve N=16 (% of n)	DIPSI-ve HbA1C-ve N=172 (% of n)
<=2.0	01(8.33%)	00	07(4.07%)
2.1-2.49	04(33.33%)	08(50%)	80(46.51%)
2.5-2.99	01(8.33%)	03(18.75%)	65(37.79%)
3.0-3.49	04(33.33%)	05(31.25%)	17(9.88%)
3.5-4.0	02(16.66%)	00	03(1.75%)
Total	12(100%)	16(100%)	172(100%)

In the present study, DIPSI negative and HbA1c negative patients had birthweights between 2 to 3 kg. Also 16% of the patients who has birth weight between 3.5 to 4 kg were GDM as compared to only 2% patients who had DIPSI and HbA1c negative.

Discussion

Table 7: Association of Risk Factors to GDM in Various Studies

Authors	Positive family h/o GDM	BMI>25 kg/m ²	Age>30 yr
Jail MV	76.9%	78.8%	28.8%
Vinital Das et al	14.3%	25%	16.6%
Sheshiah et al	-	33.33%	30%
Present study	8.3%	50%	75%

Sheshiah [7] et al noted increase in the prevalence of GDM in their study and attributed it to increased BMI, as high maternal weight is associated with a substantially higher risk of GDM.

Jang [8] et al found that the GDM women were older, had higher pre pregnancy weight, higher BMI, higher parities and higher frequencies of known diabetes in the family. Of all the independent risk factors for GDM, BMI emerged as a modi-

fiable risk factor. Solomon CG [9] et al study showed advanced maternal age, family history of diabetes mellitus, nonwhite ethnicity, higher BMI, weight gain in early adulthood and cigarette smoking predicts increased GDM risk and this observations facilitate the identification of women at particular risk for GDM and suggests potential strategies for reducing the risk even before a women becomes pregnant such as avoiding substantial weight gain and smoking.

Table 8: Maternal Complications in GDM in Pregnancy

Authors	Polyhydramnios	PIH
S Agrawal [10] et al	14.75%	31.96%
Usha Krishna [11]	6.6%	21%
Pinto. R [12]	36.6%	15.5%
Jindal et al	28%	48%
Present study	25%	50%

The most significant maternal risk with GDM is the 35-50% probability of developing type II diabetes later in life.

Table 9: Comparative Study of Perinatal Mortality

Author	Still Birth	Neonatal Death	Congenital Anomalies	Perinatal Mortality
Agrawal et al	1%	-	3%	-
Peel & Oakley	-	-	6.3%	40.3%
Pinto. R	15.5%	11.2%	5.7%	26.7%
Nanavati	4.8%	9.6%	4.8%	14.4%
Present study	0	0	16.67%	0

Schafer [13] et al reported an increased incidence of anomalies commonly associated with type I diabetes mellitus in women with either GDM or type II diabetes mellitus. The anomalies were associated with fasting hyperglycaemia and elevated HbA1C values and may represent women with undiagnosed pregestational type II diabetes mellitus. Thankfully we did not encounter any maternal or perinatal mortality.

Conclusion

The DIPSI criteria used in this study is feasible, cost effective, without compromising the clinical equipoise and can be used to diagnose the GDM in our setting and our population. It can also be used as an effective tool for early detection of glucose intolerance in peripheral and less equipped areas. Hence effective management and optimal glycaemic control helps in decreasing the maternal and perinatal mortality and morbidity.

Universal screening and management by a team approach comprising of an obstetrician, diabetologist, anaesthetist, physician and neonatologist can avoid foetal- neonatal – maternal morbidity and mortality associated with pregnancy with diabetes.

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